

Supplemental Appendix 1

Search Terms used for Scopus (A) and Web of Science (B):

A. TITLE-ABS-KEY (("paleo*" AND "niche") OR ("palaeo*" AND "niche") OR ("hindcasting" AND "niche") OR ("fossil" AND "niche") OR ("paleo" AND "enm") OR ("palaeo*" AND "enm") OR ("fossil" AND "enm") OR ("fossil" AND "sdm") OR ("deep" AND "time" AND "enm") OR ("deep" AND "time" AND "sdm") OR ("paleoclimat*" AND "envelope" AND "model*") OR ("palaeoclimat*" AND "envelope" AND "model*") OR ("deep" AND "time" AND "spatial" AND "model*") OR ("climat*" AND "niche" AND "model*" AND "fossil") OR ("climat*" AND "niche" AND "model*" AND "paleo*") OR ("climat*" AND "niche" AND "model*" AND "palaeo*") OR ("paleoenm") OR ("palaeoenm") OR ("paleodistribution") OR ("palaeodistribution") OR ("climat*" AND "niche" AND "overlap" AND "fossil") OR ("climat*" AND "niche" AND "overlap" AND "paleo*") OR ("climat*" AND "niche" AND "overlap" AND "palaeo*") OR ("bioclimatic" AND "paleo*") OR ("bioclimatic" AND "palaeo*") OR ("bioclimatic" AND "fossil") OR ("bioenvelope" AND "paleo*") OR ("bioenvelope" AND "palaeo*") OR ("bioenvelope" AND "fossil") OR ("ecological" AND "niche" AND "model*" AND "fossil") OR ("ecological" AND "niche" AND "model*" AND "paleo*") OR ("ecological" AND "niche" AND "model*" AND "palaeo*") OR ("ecological" AND "niche" AND "model*" AND "historic") OR ("distribution" AND "model*" AND "paleo*") OR ("distribution" AND "model*" AND "palaeo*") OR ("distribution" AND "model*" AND "historic") OR ("distribution" AND "model*" AND "fossil")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE,"final")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ch")) AND (LIMIT-TO (

SUBJAREA,"ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"AGRI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"EART") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"BIOC")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English")) AND (EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Fossil Fuels") OR EXCLUDE (EXACTKEYWORD,"Fossil Fuel"))

B. TS = ((paleo* AND niche) OR (palaeo* AND niche) OR (hindcasting AND niche) OR (fossil AND niche) OR (paleo AND enm) OR (palaeo* AND enm) OR (fossil AND enm) OR (fossil AND sdm) OR (deep AND time AND enm) OR (deep AND time AND sdm) OR (paleoclimat* AND envelope AND model*) OR (palaeoclimat* AND envelope AND model*) OR (deep AND time AND spatial AND model*) OR (climat* AND niche AND model* AND fossil) OR (climat* AND niche AND model* AND paleo*) OR (climat* AND niche AND model* AND palaeo*) OR (paleoenm) OR (palaeoenm) OR (paleodistribution) OR (palaeodistribution) OR (climat* AND niche AND overlap AND fossil) OR (climat* AND niche AND overlap AND paleo*) OR (climat* AND niche AND overlap AND palaeo*) OR (bioclimatic AND paleo*) OR (bioclimatic AND palaeo*) OR (bioclimatic AND fossil) OR (bioenvelope AND paleo*) OR (bioenvelope AND palaeo*) OR (bioenvelope AND fossil) OR (ecological AND niche AND model* AND fossil) OR (ecological AND niche AND model* AND paleo*) OR (ecological AND niche AND model* AND palaeo*) OR (ecological AND niche AND model* AND historic) OR (distribution AND model* AND paleo*) OR (distribution AND model* AND palaeo*) OR (distribution AND model* AND historic) OR (distribution AND model* AND fossil))

Limited to language == English and document type == Article